

DIGITAL-EUROHPC-JU-2022-NCC-01

CASTIEL 2 – Coordination & Support for National Competence Centres on a European Level Phase 2

Project Number: 101102047

D5.4

Explanatory report on initial launch of the C2ISS and
the evolved EuroCC Access Portal

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) and Germany, Austria, Italy, Spain, France and Estonia, under grant agreement No 101102047.

Work Package:	5	Awareness Creation, Impact and Outreach
Author(s):	Abdul Basit Paracha and Yinyin Ma	USTUTT
Contributor(s):	WP5 Members	
Approved by	Project Management Team	20.02.2025
Reviewer	Maria Ribera Sancho Samsó	BSC
Reviewer	Barbara Beltrán Torres	USTUTT
Dissemination Level	Public	

Date	Author	Comments	Version	Status
15/12/2024	Abdul Paracha and Yinyin Ma	Skeleton version	0.1	Draft
17/01/2025	Abdul Paracha and Yinyin Ma	Draft with technical details	0.5	Draft
20/01/2025	Abdul Paracha and Yinyin Ma	First draft for reviews	0.8	Draft
11/02/2025	Abdul Paracha and Yinyin Ma	Final draft	0.9	Draft
20/02/2025	Abdul Paracha and Yinyin Ma	Final version for submission	1.0	Final

List of Abbreviations

BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center
C2ISS	CASTIEL 2 Information Sharing System
CoE	Centre of Excellence
CMS	Content Management System
D	Deliverable
HLRS	University of Stuttgart - High Performance Computing Center
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HPC SPECTRA	High-Performance Computing Skills Platform and European Collaboration for Training
M	Month
NCC	National Competence Centre
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The document *D5.4 Explanatory Report on the Initial Launch of the EU HPC Portal and the Evolved EuroCC Access Portal* is the fourth deliverable of CASTIEL 2's Work Package 5 (WP5): Awareness, Impact, and Outreach. This deliverable provides an updated overview of the development and progress of the CASTIEL 2 Information Sharing System (C2ISS), now officially renamed the *HPC in Europe Portal*¹, and the evolved EuroCC ACCESS Portal, building upon the foundations established in previous deliverables, D5.2². This deliverable is submitted delayed (M25), due to implementation challenges occurring in 2023 and 2024, which have already been laid out during the First Project Review in February 2024.

The *HPC in Europe Portal* (previous working title “CASTIEL 2 Information Sharing System” C2ISS) is designed to serve as a central hub for information on EU-funded HPC actors, addressing the current fragmentation of information and web resources within the HPC ecosystem. The platform aims to enhance the visibility, accessibility, and coordination of information among National Competence Centres (NCCs), Centres of Excellence (CoEs), HPC projects, and other stakeholders within the HPC community. This document outlines the significant progress made in implementing the *HPC in Europe Portal* framework, including the integration of content from NCCs, CoEs, and HPC projects.

Additionally, this deliverable provides updated information on the platform's context and alignment with other existing platforms and solutions. Key achievements highlighted in the report include technical and structural implementation milestones, initial user engagement activities, and preparations for the broader inclusion of additional EU-funded HPC initiatives in subsequent project phases.

This document not only reviews the progress achieved to date but also outlines the next steps in the development of the *HPC in Europe Portal* as a fully functional and widely adopted resource, which will be further reported in deliverable D5.6 (due M30).

Key Achievements:

- First version of *HPC in Europe Portal* (formerly known as C2ISS) platform is live and initial phase of testing is in process (portal development technology: Drupal 10).
- Known bugs (backend/frontend) are being fixed.
- Content data from EuroCC-Access and HPC CoE portal are being transferred.
- Admin-user accounts representing to each NCC/CoE have been set up.
- All NCCs and CoEs profiles have been set up.

¹ HPC in Europe Portal: <https://hpc-portal.eu/>.

² CASTIEL 2 project deliverable D5.2: “Design strategy of the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC Access Portal”.

Table of Contents

1 Introduction	7
2 The workflows of backend development	9
2.1 Foundation and deployment preparation	9
2.2 User roles and user registration	10
2.3 Process for joining an organisation	16
2.4 Types of content in the HPC in Europe Portal	21
2.5 “My NCC”: Internal organisation information and tools	27
3 Homepages, Landings and Listing Pages	28
3.1 Organisation homepages, landing and listing pages	28
3.1.1 NCC Profile page	30
3.1.2 CoE Profile page	31
3.1.3 Projects’ Profile Page	32
3.2 Content-specific landing pages	32
3.2.1 Materials landing page	32
3.2.2 News & events landing page	34
3.3 Support and additional resource pages	35
3.3.1 Support landing page (Competence Map, Code, Competences)	35
3.3.2 Additional resource pages	35
3.3.3 Filtering and navigation features	36
3.3.4 Some other interactive features	37
3.4 Training pages	40
3.4.1 HPC training listing page	40
3.4.2 Training material listing page	42
3.4.3 Skill-set listing page	42
3.4.4 Element/module listing page	43
3.4.5 Track listing page	44
4 Conclusion & Outlook	45

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Website of EuroCC Access (NCCs).....	7
Figure 2 - Website of Centres of Excellence (CoEs).	7
Figure 3 – New HPC in Europe Portal (left) development structure.....	9
Figure 4 - A broad overview of the structure of the HPC in Europe Portal (formerly known as C2ISS).	13
Figure 5 - User Registration and Approval Workflow in the new HPC in Europe Portal.	13
Figure 6 - User Registration form.	14
Figure 7 – User Dashboard.....	15
Figure 8 - Joining organisation as admin/member.	18
Figure 9 - Organisation-Admin dashboard.....	19
Figure 10 - Organisation-Member dashboard.	19
Figure 11 - Organisation Profile (Data Structure).....	20
Figure 12 - Material (Data Structure).....	22
Figure 13 - Event (Data Structure).....	23
Figure 14 - Code (Data Structure).....	24
Figure 15 – Project Report (Data Structure).....	25
Figure 16 - News & Blog (Data Structure).	25
Figure 17 - Competences (Data Structure).....	26
Figure 18 - “My NCC” Dashboard.....	28
Figure 19 - Organisation homepage (NCC/CoE/Project).....	29
Figure 20 - NCC Profile page.....	30
Figure 21 - CoE Profile page.....	31
Figure 22 - Material Landing page.....	33
Figure 23 - News & Events Landing page.	34
Figure 24 - Filtering options on listing pages.....	37
Figure 25 - Contact details on Profile and Content pages.	38
Figure 26 - Video upload as a part of content.	39
Figure 27 - Text editor.....	39
Figure 28 - Training (Data Structure).....	41
Figure 29 - Training Material (Data Structure).	42
Figure 30 - Skill Set (Data Structure).....	43
Figure 31 - Element/Module (Data Structure).....	44
Figure 32 - Track (Data Structure).....	44
Figure 33 - Integration of Spectra (Indico) into HPC in Europe Portal (C2ISS).	45

List of Tables

Table 1 - Overview of User Roles.....	11
Table 2 - Overview of deliverables.	47
Table 3 - Overview of CASTIEL2 WP5 milestones.	47

1 Introduction

The *HPC in Europe Portal* (formerly known as C2ISS) is envisioned as the central access point for information on EU-funded HPC actors, aiming to enhance the visibility and accessibility of these projects significantly. It is operated by the project CASTIEL 2. By consolidating fragmented resources into a unified platform, the portal seeks to streamline access to key information for stakeholders across the HPC ecosystem and serve as an innovative tool for fostering collaboration, facilitating knowledge exchange, and showcasing the achievements of EU-funded HPC initiatives.

Currently, the dissemination of information is highly fragmented, as National Competence Centres (NCCs) and Centres of Excellence (CoEs) operate through separate websites ³ (figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1- Website of EuroCC Access (NCCs).

Figure 2 - Website of Centres of Excellence (CoEs).

³ <https://www.hpccoe.eu/eu-hpc-centres-of-excellence2/>.

Other than the fragmented information, the existing platforms mentioned above operated by the current (“old”) HPC portal⁴, National Competence Centres (NCCs) and Centres of Excellence (CoEs) also lack a comprehensive overview of HPC centres and machines in Europe, including their specifications and accessibility for different target groups such as academia, public administration, big industry and SMEs. This information, when scattered across multiple sources, limits users’ ability to fully understand the resources available and make informed decisions about their utilisation³. Furthermore, the platforms do not adequately explain how different projects and initiatives are interconnected, making it difficult for stakeholders to grasp the broader landscape and understand how their efforts contribute to the overall objectives of the HPC ecosystem.

These shortcomings collectively result in a fragmented, inefficient, and often frustrating user experience. Without these key functionalities, stakeholders struggle to navigate the complex landscape of European HPC, access critical information, and engage effectively with the community. Addressing these gaps in the new *HPC in Europe Portal* will not only enhance accessibility and coherence but also foster a more connected and collaborative HPC ecosystem, aligning with the overarching goals of the CASTIEL 2 project.

To overcome these shortcomings, it is essential to integrate these dispersed resources into a single, centralised platform to enhance accessibility, coherence, and user engagement. By consolidating information, the new portal will not only streamline access to HPC-related knowledge but also ensure that stakeholders can navigate the ecosystem more efficiently. This approach will eliminate redundancies, foster better collaboration, and create a more cohesive and interconnected environment for HPC professionals, researchers, and other stakeholders. Moreover, it will enable a more structured dissemination process, aligning with the long-term strategic goals of EU-funded HPC initiatives.

The new *HPC in Europe Portal* has been conceptualised with a structured, well-defined architecture to meet these objectives. The following diagram (Figure 3) provides a detailed visualisation of the portal’s structure, showcasing its core components, functionalities, and relationships. This visual representation serves as a blueprint for how information is organised and integrated, ensuring that all relevant HPC resources - ranging from competence centres and training programs to regulatory frameworks and expert directories - are accessible in a clear and user-friendly manner. By offering a comprehensive and intuitive framework, the portal is designed to bridge existing gaps, enhance usability, and support the EU HPC community in a more effective and sustainable way. The detailed structure of new features and functionalities in a *HPC in Europe Portal* (formerly known as C2ISS) can be viewed in the given workflow diagram.

⁴ the former (operated by PRACE) and the new HPC in Europe Portal (operated by CASTIEL 2) use the same URL: <https://hpc-portal.eu/>. At the time of submitting this deliverable, the domain is already operated by CASTIEL 2.

Figure 3 – New HPC in Europe Portal (left) development structure at a glance.

2 The workflows of backend development

2.1 Foundation and deployment preparation

The first step in developing the *HPC in Europe Portal* was to retrieve the existing HPC-Portal code and set up a dedicated server at HLRS (High-Performance Computing Center, University of Stuttgart).

Since the portal is not being built from scratch but upgraded with additional features and functionalities, the initial requirement was to access the existing codebase at BSC (Barcelona Supercomputing Centre) and deploy it on a new server at HLRS. However, transferring the code to the latest development environment posed several technical and legal challenges, leading to delays. Despite these obstacles, the process was successfully completed and *hpc-portal.eu* was deployed on new server at HLRS in September 2024 through the collective efforts of the *HPC in Europe Portal* development and management teams.

Another critical technical requirement was upgrading Drupal⁵, an open-source content management system (CMS) used for building, managing, and customising websites and digital platforms to its latest version (Drupal 10) before proceeding with further development. After retrieving the code from BSC, the system was first migrated from Drupal 8 to Drupal 10 and then successfully deployed on the new HLRS server.

In addition to technical challenges, several non-technical obstacles also contributed to delays. These included procurement delays on the university's administrative side (USTUTT) and decision-making bottlenecks from both technical and non-technical stakeholders. The legal challenge was posed by the necessity to sign an agreement or, memorandum of understanding (MoU), between all engaged parties who needed access to the old HPC in Europe Portal backend and domain. Further delays arose from restricted access to the existing codebase and the transfer of domain rights needed for hosting the portal at HLRS.

With these challenges successfully resolved, the portal development progressed, introducing substantial enhancements and structural improvements. The next phase focused on implementing new features and functionalities to enhance usability, accessibility, and performance. In the following sections, we specify the workflows of backend development that drive these improvements, detailing the key components and processes that shape the *HPC in Europe Portal*.

2.2 User roles and user registration

First and foremost, to access the features and functionalities of the *HPC in Europe Portal*, users are required to register an account. Once a registration form is submitted, the portal administrator will review and approve the request. Upon approval, users gain access to their user dashboard, where they can create and manage content based on their assigned roles. Below, we outline the concepts of user roles and workflows for user registration functionalities.

On the new *HPC in Europe Portal*, users are categorised into distinct roles, each with specific permissions and responsibilities:

⁵ Drupal CMS for Ambitious Marketing: <https://new.drupal.org/home>.

User Type	Activities can perform
Organisation-Admin	Access User-Dashboard, Create User Profile, Manage Organisation Profile, manage Organisation-members, create and manage own content
Organisation-Member	Access User-Dashboard, Create User Profile, create and manage own content
Training Provider	Access User-Dashboard, Create User Profile, create and manage own contents (Training / Training Material)
Attendee	Access User-Dashboard, Create User Profile
Content Manager	Access User-Dashboard, manage contents (update/unpublish/delete any content)
User Manager	Access User-Dashboard, manage (activate/block any user)

Table 1. Overview of User Roles

a. Organisation-Admin user

This user role represents an administrator managing an HPC-related organisation.

There are three types of Organisations: NCCs, CoEs and Projects. One responsibility of the Organisation-Admin user is to manage the organisation's profile page, where all content related to the organisation (NCC/CoE/Project) is displayed, including research outputs, events, and training materials.

- Approves new members requesting to join their affiliated NCCs (National Competence Centres), CoEs (Centres of Excellence), or Projects.
- Can create and manage content on behalf of their organisation, including news, research publications, training materials, and events.
- Has the ability to create user profiles for new members.

b. Organisation-Member user

This user role is a general member within an HPC-related organisation who contributes content to the portal.

Can create and publish a wide range of content, including:

- Events
- HPC-related Code and Materials (Use cases, success stories, video galleries, documents)
- Project reports, news, blogs
- Training and training materials
- Can create and update their own user profile.
- Members are linked to their organisation's profile page, where their contributions are aggregated and displayed.
- Can join a single NCC.
- Can join multiple CoEs simultaneously.

- Can join multiple Projects simultaneously, allowing for cross-institutional collaboration and engagement across different HPC initiatives.

c. Training Provider user

This user role is for users responsible for organising and managing training programs related to HPC. It is only assigned to users who are not affiliated with any organisation.

- Can create content specifically related to:
 - Training Sessions
 - Training Materials
- Can create and update their own user profile.

d. Attendee user

This user role is a user interested in attending HPC-related training sessions.

- Can create and update their own user profile.
- In Attendee Corner:
 - Their data is categorised based on their Scientific Domain and Pre-requisite Skill Set.
 - This information helps match them with relevant upcoming training events tailored to their background and interests.

e. Content Manager

This user role oversees and maintains all content published on the portal.

- Can review, edit, publish/unpublish, archive, or delete any content created by users.
- Ensures that published content meets the platform's quality standards and relevance.
- Can create/manage Competences data, which would be displayed in Competence-Map

f. User Manager

This user role is that of an administrator responsible for managing user accounts and platform access control.

- Manages all user accounts and their associated information.
- Has the authority to approve, block, activate, or deactivate user accounts based on policy compliance. In policy violations or misuse cases, a user account may be blocked or removed to maintain platform integrity.

To become a portal user, one must follow a structured registration process. To further illustrate the user registration process and the associated approval workflow, the following diagram (Fig. 5) visually represents the steps involved in onboarding different user roles within the *HPC in Europe Portal*. Each user type follows a structured registration process that requires form submission, approval from relevant administrators, and eventual access to the user dashboard, where they can create and manage content. This diagram features three main user registration

paths: Organisation Users (NCC/CoE/Project members), Training Provider Users and Attendee Users.

Figure 4 - A broad overview of the structure of the HPC in Europe Portal (formerly known as C2ISS).

Figure 5 - User Registration and Approval Workflow in the new HPC in Europe Portal.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the User Registration form and the dashboard for users, once the registration is successful.

Figure 6 - User Registration form.

The screenshot shows a user dashboard for 'TEST-TK'. At the top left is a 'User Dashboard' button. The header includes 'HPC EUROPE' and navigation links: 'ABOUT', 'SERVICES', 'HPC IN EUROPE', 'TRAINING', 'SUPPORT', 'NEWS', and 'MATERIALS'. The main content is organized into sections: 'MY NCC' (Stuttgart, Germany) with a profile card for 'NCC GERMANY'; 'MY COES' (Barcelona, Spain and Berlin, Germany) with profile cards for 'CHEESE' and 'NOMAD'; 'MY PROJECTS' (Berlin, Germany) with a profile card for 'IRIS ADLERSHOF'; 'MY INVITATIONS' (no invitations available); and 'MY CONTENT' with a table of entries. The table has columns for 'NEW', 'EDIT', and 'DELETE'.

TESTING CODE	NEW	EDIT	DELETE
NEWS: CODE			
NCC GERMANY			
17/01/2025			
RESEARCH BREAKTHROUGH	NEW	EDIT	DELETE
NEWS: NEWS ENTRY			
NCC GERMANY			
19/10/2024			

Figure 7 – User Dashboard.

2.3 Process for joining an organisation

Concept of *Organisation* and how to join *Organisation*

- There are three types of Organisation entities: **NCCs, CoEs and Projects.**
- Each Organisation has two user levels: **Organisation-Admin** and **Organisation-Member.**
- Each Organisation has its Profile page where all the contents belonging to this Organisation (NCC/CoE/Project) will be displayed.
- The contact details of every Organisation will also be displayed on the profile page.
- Registered users can join a single NCC, multiple CoEs, and various Projects simultaneously.

Section 2.2 highlighted the different user roles within the *HPC in Europe Portal*, including Organisation-Admins and Organisation-Members, who are responsible for managing and contributing to an organisation's content. It is important to note that users must be affiliated with at least one organisation to perform any functions on the portal. In this section, we explain how users can join an organisation, either as an admin or a member.

To ensure proper user onboarding and role assignment, the *HPC in Europe Portal* provides multiple pathways for users to join an organisation. Depending on their role and access level, users may either be assigned an admin role by the User Manager to request membership through different mechanisms.

Organisation entities	Admin-User activities	Member-User activities
NCC/CoE/Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can update Profile (NCC/CoE/Project) • Invite external user to join their belonging Organisation • Approve request to join Organisation • Remove Member from Organisation • Create content for belonging Organisation • Update belonging content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can create content for belonging NCC • Update own created content

Table 2 Organisation Admin/Member Activities

Below is an outline of four primary methods available for joining an organisation.

1. **Joining an organisation as an admin:**

The creation of Organisation-Admin accounts is handled directly by the portal administrator at the backend to ensure administrative control over each organisation. The process follows these steps:

- The portal administrator creates an Organisation-Admin account and sends credentials to the nominated user (admin will be nominated by the NCC/CoE/Project, whoever they want to make admin, they need to inform portal administrator).
- The portal admin also creates an organisation profile and assigns Organisation-Admin rights to a nominated user.

- Upon first login, the Organisation-Admin is responsible for setting up their organisation profile, including contact details, research focus, and organisational content.
- The Organisation-Admin can then manage their organisation's members, content, and overall presence on the portal.

This process ensures that only authorised individuals are given admin rights to oversee their organisation's participation in the portal.

2. Joining an organisation as a member through registration:

Users can directly join an organisation at the time of registration by following these steps:

- While filling out the registration form, the user selects their affiliated NCC, CoE, or Project from the available list under the 'Organisation Type' field.
- Once the registration form is submitted, a joining request is automatically sent to the Organisation-Admin for approval.
- The Organisation-Admin reviews the request and can either approve or reject it.
- After the Organisation-Admin approves the request, the portal administrator reviews and grants final approval, enabling the user to access the portal as an Organisation-Member.
- Upon approval, the user is granted Organisation-Member status and gains access to the organisation's content.

This method ensures that members are validated before being assigned to an organisation, maintaining structured access control.

3. Joining an organisation as a member by sending a request to the Organisation-Admin:

If the user wants to join an additional organisation as a member (any CoE/Project or NCC, if the user does not belong to any NCC), then the user can proceed with the following steps:

- Visiting the organisation profile page of their desired NCC, CoE, or Project.
- Sending a membership request to the Organisation-Admin via the organisation profile page.
- The Organisation-Admin reviews and either approves or declines the request.
- Upon approval, the user is assigned an Organisation-Member status.

This method allows users to join additional organisations at any time after registration, ensuring flexibility in participation.

4. Joining an organisation as a member by receiving an invitation from the Organisation-Admin:

Organisation-Admins can also invite external users to join their organisation through a direct invitation process:

- The Organisation-Admin sends an email invitation to the external user.
- If a user accepts the invitation and is already registered at the portal, he will automatically become a member of that organisation without performing any extra steps.

- If a user accepts the invitation but is not registered at the portal, then he would be required to fill out the portal registration form and submit it to the portal admin.
- After approval from the portal administrator, he will become a member of that organisation.

Note: User can join only one NCC with a single user-ID but can join more than one CoE or Project with a single user-ID).

This method simplifies onboarding by allowing organisations to recruit new members proactively and streamline their engagement.

To further illustrate the process of joining an organisation within the *HPC in Europe Portal*, the following diagram visually represents the steps involved for both Organisation-Admins and Organisation-Members. It details the different pathways users can take, whether through portal admin assignment, direct registration, user-initiated requests, or admin invitations. Each step highlights the necessary approvals and actions required to gain access to the organisation's dashboard, ensuring a structured and secure onboarding process.

Figure 8 - Joining organisation as admin/member.

NCC Finland content ☆

View Edit Members Membership requests Invitations Content

Add new content

Add.Event Add.News.Entry Add.Material Add.Code Add.Project.Report

Published status: - Any - Type: - Any - Apply

View Edit Members Membership requests Invitations Content

No membership requests available.

Title	Content type	Status	Updated	Operations
Test Content 002	(new) Material	Published	07/02/2025 - 11:38 CET	Edit node
Test Content 001	(new) News Entry	Published	07/02/2025 - 11:38 CET	Edit node

NCC Finland members ☆

View Edit Members Membership requests Invitations Content

Invite member Invite members Add member

User	Roles	Updated	Joined	Operations
webadmin	NCC-Admin NCC-Member	17/01/2025 - 14:39 CET	17/01/2025 - 14:39 CET	View member
hpcapara	NCC-Admin	17/01/2025 - 18:37 CET	17/01/2025 - 18:37 CET	View member
hpcportal-test2	NCC-Member	17/01/2025 - 18:51 CET	17/01/2025 - 18:51 CET	View member

Email	Invitee	Roles	Invited by	Invited on	Operations
test1.hpcportal@gmail.com	Anonymous User (not verified)	NCC-Member	hpcapara	17/01/2025 - 18:52 CET	Remove invitation

Invitee mail: user_test01@testdomain.com

Roles: NCC-Admin NCC-Member

Select invitees: test-user-01, test-user-02, user03.test@testdomain.com

Submit Back to group

Figure 9 - Organisation-Admin dashboard.

NCC Finland content

View Content

Add.Event Add.News.Entry Add.Material Add.Code Add.Project.Report

Published status: - Any - Type: - Any - Apply

Title	Content type	Status	Updated	Operations
Test Content 07	(new) Material	Published	07/02/2025 - 14:06 CET	Edit node
Test Content 06	(new) Competences	Published	07/02/2025 - 14:06 CET	Edit node
Test Content 002	(new) Material	Published	07/02/2025 - 11:38 CET	
Test Content 001	(new) News Entry	Published	07/02/2025 - 11:38 CET	

Figure 10 - Organisation-Member dashboard.

Organisation Profile (NCC/CoE/Project)	
Field Title	Data Type
Ttile	Text Field
Organization Logo	Image Field (Drupal default image)
Brief Description	Text Area
Related Images	Image Field (Drupal default image)
Related Video	Upload File
Related Video	Video Link
Address (Street Add)	Text Address
City	Select List (Texonomy)
Country	Select List (Texonomy)
Email Add (Organization)	Email Field
Web	Link Field
Social Media Links (Facebook,Linkedin, X(Twitter), Youtube)	Social Links (Module)
Tags	Term (Texonomy)

Figure 11 - Organisation Profile (Data Structure).

2.4 Types of content in the HPC in Europe Portal

In the previous sections, we discussed user roles within the portal (2.2) and the process of joining an organisation (2.3). Once users gain access, they can create, manage, and interact with various types of content available on the platform.

The new *HPC in Europe Portal* is a comprehensive knowledge hub that facilitates the exchange of expertise, research findings, training materials, events, and project-related content. This section provides an overview of the portal's different content types, detailing their structure and intended use.

a. Materials

The portal supports various material types, enabling users to upload, share, and reference key resources, including:

- Publications: Documents containing insights, best practices, and research outcomes, including:
 - Use cases & success stories – real-world applications of HPC solutions.
 - Whitepapers – in-depth reports exploring technical aspects of HPC.
 - Best practice guides – guidelines on effective HPC usage.
- Documents: A categorised collection of reports and reference materials, including:
 - Best practices – guides for optimising HPC workflows.
 - Training materials – learning resources for HPC professionals.
 - Summaries of workshops – documentation of key discussions and findings from past events.
- Media: Multimedia content for training, promotion, and technical demonstrations, with the following options:
 - Uploaded video – directly uploaded videos by users.
 - Linked video – external video links can be embedded.
 - Presentation slides – accompanying slide decks can be attached for reference.
- Tools: Repository of helpful software tools and resources, including:
 - Tool descriptions – brief overview of each tool.
 - Tool links – direct access to tools hosted externally.

The graph depicting the material data structure is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 - Material (Data Structure).

b. Events

The portal allows users to create and manage various events, which can be categorised as follows:

- Event types: Events can be in-person, online, or hybrid.

- Start and end dates: specifies event duration.
 - Event location: city and country for in-person events.
 - Registration link: directs users to the sign-up page.
- Add to calendar option: Enables easy scheduling for attendees.

The corresponding Event data structure is laid out below, in Figure 13:

Figure 13 - Event (Data Structure).

c. Code

The portal facilitates sharing and categorising HPC-related code, ensuring visibility and accessibility for users. Each code entry includes (the data structure for input type “code” is shown in Figure 14):

- Application area: the specific scientific or industrial field where the code is used.
- Scalability: the extent to which the code supports parallel computing and HPC scalability.
- Legal & licensing information: details on software usage rights.
- Related training & support: links to relevant training and technical support.
- Related success stories & use cases: demonstrating the code’s real-world applications.
- External code link: direct access to repositories or official sources.

Field Title	Code	Data Type
Title		Default Title
Description		Text Area
Application Area/Areas		Select List
Scalability Information		Text Area
Availability on JU systems		Select List
Legal / Licensing info		Text Area
TRL		Integer
Related Training		Ref Content
Related Support(Competences)		Ref Content
Related Success Stories/Use Cases		Ref Content
External Link		Link

Figure 14 - Code (Data Structure).

d. Project reports

This section allows users to upload and share project documentation, including (see Figure 15 for data structure):

- File uploads (PDF) – direct submission of project reports.
- Report description – a summary of the document’s content.

Figure 15 – Project Report (Data Structure).

e. News & Blogs

A dedicated space for sharing HPC-related news, updates, and blog posts to keep the community informed about recent developments and discussions (see Figure 16).

Figure 16 - News & Blog (Data Structure).

f. Competences

The Competence Map provides an interactive overview of expertise, services, and facilities within the High-Performance Computing (HPC) ecosystem. The competence section categorises user expertise and provides structured information, including (see Figure 17):

- Experience level – users can specify beginner, intermediate, or advanced levels.
- Competence categories – various domains of HPC expertise.
- Competences will be created and managed by the Content Manager.
- An interactive Competence Map is available to identify the services availability and their providers in an easy-to-explore manner.

Figure 17 - Competences (Data Structure).

g. Training

The portal provides a structured repository for training resources, including:

- Training sessions - scheduled learning opportunities.
- Training materials - learning resources, including slides, documents, and recorded sessions.

The development of the training platform involves HPC SPECTRA, a project partner responsible for developing and integrating the training framework into the *HPC in Europe Portal*. Training content will initially be created and managed on Indico⁶. This event management platform facilitates attendee registration, scheduling of training sessions (date/time) and providing registration links for training programs. Once created, all training content will be migrated to the *HPC in the Europe Portal*, where it will be displayed on a centralised Training Listing Page for easy access by users.

Additionally, training materials will be stored and shared via Zenodo⁷, an open-access repository that enables efficient storage, distribution, and long-term accessibility of training

⁶ Indico software by CERN: <https://getindico.io/>.

⁷ Zenodo digital repository: <https://zenodo.org/>.

resources. This integration ensures that all training-related content remains structured, accessible, and well-maintained within the portal.

To summarise, the portal is designed to support a wide range of content, including publications, training, events, project reports, tools, news updates and training information. Each category is crucial in knowledge sharing, training, and collaboration within the HPC community. This classification ensures that users can efficiently navigate, contribute, and access relevant resources based on their roles and interests.

2.5 “My NCC”: Internal organisation information and tools

Building upon the structured content categories outlined in Section 2.4, the *Euro HPC Portal* also provides a dedicated “My NCC” section designed only for NCCs. This section is an internal resource hub, allowing NCC members to access and manage key organisational data, administrative tools, and collaborative resources.

The “My NCC” section is available exclusively to members affiliated with an NCC and provides access to various tools and structured data to support training coordination, project tracking, budgeting, and organisational management. Below is an overview of the core components within “My NCC” (see also Figure 18).

“My NCC” listing pages	This section provides a structured directory of NCCs, allowing users to navigate and find relevant competence centres, their key activities, and available resources.
Recording directory	A comprehensive information database link of CASTIEL sessions and workshops on BSCW.
Training matrix	A link of the availability of training material.
Application Matrix	An internal database categorizing various HPC applications, helping members identify relevant tools, software, and computational resources used within their NCC.
Budget (workshop/twinning or mentoring)	An internal system where one can apply for fundings for workshop, and twinning activities.
Cluster Tool	An internal tool enables NCC members to identify which National Competence Centres (NCCs) provide

expertise in specific HPC-related services. It serves as a searchable directory, allowing users to filter services by category and domain to find an appropriate NCC partner for collaboration. The tool also provides contact information for each NCC, facilitating direct engagement for support and cooperation.

In short, the “My NCC” section serves as a critical internal resource for NCC members, providing structured access to key organisational data, financial tracking, training coordination, and research knowledge. By offering these tools, the *Euro HPC Portal* ensures that competence centres can operate efficiently, collaborate effectively, and enhance knowledge sharing across the HPC ecosystem.

Figure 18 - “My NCC” Dashboard.

3 Homepages, Landings and Listing Pages

Building upon the structured backend development and content organisation discussed in Section 2, the next phase of the *HPC in Europe Portal*’s development focuses on the visual display of information and the data representation. This section details the layout, navigation, and content presentation across different landing and listing pages, ensuring users can efficiently explore, access, and interact with the portal’s extensive resources.

3.1 Organisation homepages, landing and listing pages

The portal has multiple landing pages that serve as entry points for various user categories and content types. These pages aggregate relevant information and offer intuitive navigation for further exploration.

Organisation-related homepages (NCC/CoE/Project):

Each Organisation type has a homepage (see Figure 19 for an example) containing a list of all Organisations having the same Organisation type (NCC-Homepage, CoE Homepage, Project Homepage). It also includes a list of contents belonging to the same Organisation types (Publication, News, Training).

The screenshot displays the 'National Competence Centres' page on the HPC Europe website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for ABOUT, SERVICES, TRAINING, SUPPORT, NEWS, and MATERIALS. Below the navigation is a header with the text 'National Competence Centres' and 'NATIONAL COMPETENCE CENTRES'. A large map of Europe is shown, with several countries highlighted in blue. Below the map, there is a paragraph of text explaining the role of National Competence Centres (NCCs) in providing a central hub for high-performance computing (HPC) and related technologies. Below the text are several buttons for EVENTS, TRAININGS, SUPPORT, MATERIALS, and SUCCESS STORIES. The main content area is divided into two rows of NCC profiles. The first row includes Austria (EURO AUSTRIA), Belgium (EURO BELGIUM), Bulgaria (EURO BULGARIA), and Croatia (EURO CROATIA). The second row includes Cyprus (aStOR), Czech Republic (EURO CZECHIA), Denmark (DeiC), and Estonia (EURO ESTONIA). Below the NCC profiles is a 'LOAD MORE' button. The 'PUBLICATIONS' section follows, with a sub-header and a paragraph of text. It features three success story cards: 'SEMI-SUPERVISED LEARNING IN AERIAL IMAGE...', 'NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION FOR ADDRESS EXT...', and 'INTENT CLASSIFICATION FOR BANK CHATBOTS...'. Below the publications is an 'ALL PUBLICATIONS' button. The 'NEWS' section has a sub-header and three news cards: 'HPC WEBINAR FOR SMES: EXAMPLES OF REAL USE OF HPC IN POLAND, THE CZECH REPUBLIC AND SLOVAKIA', 'THE CROATIAN EDUCATIONAL LANDSCAPE IN THE FIELDS OF HPC, HPC/AI, AND AI', and 'EUROCC 2 & COES & CASTIEL 2 INTERMEDIATE CONFERENCE IN SLOVAKIA'. The 'BLOG' section has a sub-header and two blog cards: 'PARTICIPATE IN THE WEBINAR "CREATING AND TRAINING NEURAL NETWORKS WITH MATLAB"' and 'HPC COMPETENCE CENTRE IN LATVIA "SUPERS" ORGANIZED THE OPEN HPC WEEK FOR THE THIRD YEAR'.

Figure 19 - Organisation homepage (NCC/CoE/Project).

3.1.1 NCC Profile page

The NCC's homepage (see Figure 20) introduces the role and significance of NCCs in advancing HPC capabilities across Europe. It provides an overview of all NCCs and a directory linking to individual NCC profile pages. The page also highlights the latest contributions from NCCs, including use cases, success stories, HPC competences, events, and training sessions. A competence map visually represents expertise across various domains, helping users identify relevant research and collaboration opportunities. Additionally, visitors can stay informed through the latest news and blog updates and subscribe to the portal's newsletter for regular updates.

Each NCC has a dedicated profile page featuring an introduction section with text, images, and videos. This page aggregates the latest contributions from the respective NCC, showcasing relevant research outputs, events, and training materials. Additionally, it includes news updates, contact details, and social media links, allowing users to engage directly with the organisation.

The screenshot shows the profile page for NCC GERMANY on the HPC EUROPE portal. The page features a navigation bar with links for ABOUT, SERVICES, TRAINING, SUPPORT, NEWS, and MATERIALS. The main heading is "GERMANY". Below this, the "NCC GERMANY" section provides an introduction to EuroCC@GCS, the German national centre of competence for high-performance computing (HPC). It lists tasks such as collecting HPC training offers, developing a map of HPC competences, acting as a gateway for industry and academia, and fostering industrial uptake. A "FOR INDUSTRY" section includes an image of an industrial facility and text explaining how HPC is used to reduce development costs and improve product quality. A "FOR USERS" section features an image of two women in a server room and a welcome message about supercomputers. On the right side, there is a contact box with the address "Nobelstraße 19, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany", an email "eurocc_gms@hpc.projects.hrw.de", and a "Website" link. Below the contact box are social media links for "in X" and a map of Europe highlighting Germany's location relative to neighboring countries like France, Austria, Hungary, and Italy.

Figure 20 - NCC Profile page.

3.1.2 CoE Profile page

The Centres of Excellence (CoEs) homepage (see Figure 21) is the primary hub for research-driven HPC initiatives. Similar to the NCCs section, it features an introduction explaining the role of CoEs, followed by a complete listing of CoE profile pages. Users can explore the latest use cases, success stories, events, and training sessions curated by various CoEs. The page also includes the most recent news and blogs related to CoEs and a newsletter subscription option to inform users about ongoing projects and advancements.

Each CoE profile page provides a detailed introduction to the centre's mission, expertise, and contributions. It compiles recent research outputs, training opportunities, and events while offering direct access to news updates, contact information, and social media channels for further engagement.

The screenshot shows the CHEESE CoE profile page on the HPC Europe website. The page header includes the HPC Europe logo and navigation links: ABOUT, SERVICES, TRAINING, SUPPORT, NEWS, MATERIALS. The breadcrumb trail is Home > Centres of Excellence > CHEESE. The main heading is CHEESE. Below this, the text reads: CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN THE DOMAIN OF SOLID EARTH. CHEESE-2P intends to anchor itself as a central hub for HPC software within the solid earth community to evaluate and forecast geohazards. The project collaborates closely with European institutions, hardware developers, industry stakeholders, public bodies, and HPC centers. Stepping into its second phase, CHEESE-2P aims to prepare 11 community flagship codes to address 12 domain-specific Exascale Computational Challenges (ECCs) on, eg., computational seismology, magnetohydrodynamics, physical volcanology. Codes will be optimized in terms of performance on different types of accelerators, scalability, deployment, containerization, and portability. Codes and workflows will combine to form a new generation of 9-Pilot Demonstrators underpinned by concepts like multi-scale, multi-source, and multi-physics, that will materialise in 15 Simulation Cases representing capability and capacity use cases of particular relevance in terms of science, social relevance, or urgency. The page also features a 'LATEST CHEESE NEWS' section with three news items: 'FocusCoE at EuroHPC Summit Week 2022' (24. March 2022), 'FocusCoE Hosts Intel OneAPI Workshop for the EU HPC CoEs' (4. March 2022), and 'SIMAI 2021' (11. October 2021). A social media widget for CHEESE is visible on the right. At the bottom, there is a video player for 'CHEESE: Saving lives and mitigating the effects of natural catastrophes' with a 'Tsunami' title and a 'Tellen' logo.

Figure 21 - CoE Profile page.

3.1.3 Projects' Profile Page

The Projects' homepage acts as a centralised gateway to EU-funded HPC projects. It offers an overview of ongoing initiatives, detailing their objectives, research areas, and expected impact. Visitors can browse through a directory of project profile pages and explore the latest use cases, events, and training sessions linked to each project. Like the NCCs and CoEs sections, this page features news articles, blogs, and a newsletter subscription to ensure stakeholders stay updated on the latest project developments.

Each project profile page presents an introduction with supporting multimedia content and compiles the latest research contributions, events, and training activities. Users can find news updates, contact details, and social media links, enabling direct interaction with project representatives.

3.2 Content-specific landing pages

Beyond organization-specific sections, the portal hosts several content-focused landing pages, each dedicated to a specific type of resource.

3.2.1 Materials landing page

The Materials page serves as a structured repository for HPC-related resources, categorised into multiple sections for easy navigation (see Figure 22). Users can explore use cases, success stories, video galleries, documents, project reports, and HPC tools. Each content type has its own listing page, providing detailed descriptions and filtering options to facilitate quick access.

The screenshot displays the 'MATERIALS' landing page of the HPC Europe website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'ABOUT', 'SERVICES', 'TRAINING', 'SUPPORT', 'NEWS', and 'MATERIALS', along with a search icon. The main heading is 'MATERIALS'. Below this is a large image of server racks in a data center. A text block below the image invites users to explore materials for HPC, including success stories, guides, and technical papers. The 'PUBLICATIONS' section features three cards: 'BIOEXCEL: ELECTRONIC INTERACTION PHENOMENA: PROTON DYNAMICS AND FLUORESCENT PROTEINS', 'SEMI-SUPERVISED LEARNING IN AERIAL IMAGERY: IMPLEMENTING UNI-MATCH WITH FRAME FIELD LEARNING FOR BUILDING EXTRACTION', and 'NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION FOR ADDRESS EXTRACTION IN SPEECH-TO-TEXT TRANSCRIPTIONS USING SYNTHETIC DATA'. The 'DOCUMENTS' section lists four best practice guides for download, such as 'DO'S AND DON'TS INDUSTRY WORKSHOPS' and 'PORTFOLIO (PER SECTOR) II INDUSTRY USE CASES'. The 'PROJECT REPORTS' section lists several reports for reading, including 'CASTIEL 2: D5.5 SECOND REPORT ON AWARENESS, IMPACT AND OUTREACH'.

Figure 22 - Material Landing page.

3.2.2 News & events landing page

The News & Events section aggregates all relevant updates from the HPC ecosystem. It features a regularly updated feed of announcements, upcoming events, blog articles, and general news (see Figure 23). Users can browse individual listing pages dedicated to events, blog posts, and news articles, ensuring they can quickly find information that aligns with their interests.

Figure 23 - News & Events Landing page.

3.3 Support and additional resource pages

In addition to organization-specific and content-based sections, the *HPC in Europe Portal* provides dedicated support and resource pages that help users navigate HPC-related services, access technical expertise, and explore funding opportunities. These pages ensure that users can efficiently find the information they need, whether seeking competence mapping, industry services, or collaboration opportunities.

3.3.1 Support landing page (Competence Map, Code, Competences)

The Support page serves as a structured hub for users looking for guidance on HPC competences, technical resources, and available expertise across Europe. It introduces key competence areas and provides an overview of computational codes, enabling users to explore available HPC technologies and methodologies.

To offer a visual representation of skills and expertise distribution, the page features a Competence Map, which allows users to gain insights into the strengths of different organisations and research centres. Users can access both an overview and a more detailed version of the map, ensuring they can easily navigate specific fields of expertise.

Within this section, individual listing pages for competences and codes allow users to browse structured datasets categorised by specialisation. These listings provide a way for researchers, developers, and organisations to locate relevant expertise, tools, and software that align with their projects or training needs. By offering detailed descriptions and structured access, the Support page ensures that users can efficiently find the technical resources required for their work.

3.3.2 Additional resource pages

Beyond technical support, the portal provides several additional resource pages catering to industrial collaboration, funding opportunities, and strategic project coordination. The Services and Industrial Services sections introduce available HPC solutions designed to support businesses and research institutions. These services help industry partners integrate high-performance computing into their workflows, offering consultation, computational resources, and specialised software tools.

The Resources page serves as a knowledge repository, compiling internal and external assets relevant to the HPC community. This section includes reports, guidelines, and other useful documents that support users in developing and refining their HPC strategies. Complementing these resources, the Funding Opportunities page provides structured access to grants, investment programs, and financial support options available for HPC research and technology development. This section is particularly valuable for organisations seeking to secure funding for collaborative projects or large-scale computational initiatives.

To facilitate project coordination across Europe, the Projects + Coordination and Support Action page outlines ongoing collaborative efforts within the HPC ecosystem. This page provides details on how different EU-funded projects work together, exchange knowledge, and create synergies to drive innovation. Users can explore various initiatives, learn about best practices in project management, and identify potential collaboration partners within the HPC community.

For those looking to apply for supercomputing resources, the Supercomputing Accelerator application page offers a structured process for submitting applications. This page provides an overview of available accelerator programs, eligibility criteria, and step-by-step guidance for researchers and organisations interested in gaining access to high-performance computing infrastructure.

3.3.3 Filtering and navigation features

To ensure efficient content discovery, the *HPC in Europe Portal* incorporates advanced filtering and sorting mechanisms across all listing pages (Fig. 24). These features help users refine search results and locate relevant information quickly and effectively. Users can filter data by content type, such as events, publications or use cases, ensuring they can focus on specific resources. Additionally, filtering options allow users to sort content based on organisation affiliation, enabling them to view materials provided by specific NCCs, CoEs, or Projects.

A date filtration system enhances usability by allowing users to browse content published within a specific timeframe. This feature is particularly useful for researchers and professionals seeking the most up-to-date information on training sessions, funding calls, or technical breakthroughs. The portal also includes a keyword search function, enabling users to retrieve content by searching for specific terms found in the title of any document, event, or training session.

By integrating structured filtering and navigation options, the *HPC in Europe Portal* ensures that users can efficiently access relevant HPC-related resources (see Figure 24). Whether searching for funding opportunities, technical competences, or industrial services, visitors can tailor their experience to meet their specific needs.

Filtering options

Filtering on **Publication**

FILTERS

TITLE

AFTER BEFORE

PUBLISHED BY CATEGORY

Filtering on **Videos**

FILTERS

TITLE

AFTER BEFORE

PUBLISHED BY

Filtering on **Events**

FILTERS

TITLE

AFTER BEFORE

CITY COUNTRY

TYPE ORGANIZED BY

Filtering on **Competences**

FILTERS

TITLE

EXPERIENCE COMPETENCE

PROVIDED BY

Figure 24 - Filtering options on listing pages.

3.3.4 Some other interactive features

There are many interactive features available to make portal use easy and convenient for every user. Some of them include:

Contact detail section

Each Organisation user (NCC/CoE/Project) can publish their contact details on their profile (see Figure 25), including address location with map, email/website link, social media links including LinkedIn, X(Twitter), YouTube channels, Instagram and Facebook.

Figure 25 - Contact details on Profile and Content pages.

Upload Videos

In Material content user can upload their videos or also linked a video from external source like YouTube or Vimeo (see Figure 26).

Figure 26 - Video upload as a part of content.

CKEditor

CKEditor is available, which will help to create rich text content correctly, and it also makes it possible to add images, videos, or development code like HTML/PHP, etc., to the text of content (see Figure 27).

Figure 27 - Text editor

3.4 Training pages

The HPC training section in *Europe Portal* serves as a central hub for high-performance computing (HPC) education and skills development, providing structured access to training programs, learning materials, and skill-building opportunities. The portal organises training-related content into distinct listing pages to facilitate navigation and ensure a seamless learning experience. These pages allow users to explore available training sessions, access educational materials, and track their progress based on skill levels and specialised training paths.

3.4.1 HPC training listing page

The HPC Training Listing Page provides an overview of all upcoming and past training sessions available through the portal (see Figure 28). Users can browse a comprehensive directory of training events, filtering them based on relevant criteria such as training provider, organisation affiliation (NCC, CoE, Project), topic, and date. Each training session entry includes details such as course descriptions, target audience, prerequisites, instructors, and registration links. This page serves as the primary reference point for users looking to enrol in HPC training sessions, whether beginners seeking foundational knowledge or advanced users aiming to refine their expertise in specialised areas.

Training Content	
Field Title	Data Type
Title of Training	Default Title
Training Description	Text Area
Training Image	Image Field
Start Date & Time	Date field
End Date & Time	Date field
Registration Link	Link
Event Type	Term (Taxonomy)
Address	Text Area
City	Term (Taxonomy)
Country	Term (Taxonomy)
Language	Term (Taxonomy)
Level	List
Fees (if applicable)	Free Text
Organiser	Ref-User
Co-Organisers	List
Existing User	Ref-User
Non-existing User	Term (Taxonomy)
Skills	Ref-Link
Scientific Domain	List
Pre-requisites (logistics)	Text Area
Pre-requisites (skills)	Ref-Link
Sector of the Target Audience	List
HPC Profile of Target Audience	List
Related Training	Ref-Link
Related Material	Ref-Link

Figure 28 - Training (Data Structure).

3.4.2 Training material listing page

The Training Material Listing Page offers a structured repository of educational resources, making it easy for users to access learning materials related to HPC (see Figure 29). This page includes slides, recorded lectures, documentation, tutorials, and technical guides that support self-paced learning. Additionally, integration with Zenodo, an open-access repository, ensures that training materials are well-organized, easily accessible, and maintained for long-term availability.

Figure 29 - Training Material (Data Structure).

3.4.3 Skill-set listing page

To help users identify relevant training opportunities, the Skill-Set Listing Page categorises training content based on specific competences and proficiency levels (see Figure 30). Users can explore skill-based classifications to determine which training sessions align with their current knowledge and learning goals. Each skill set includes a description of the required prerequisites, expected learning outcomes, and applicable HPC domains, allowing users to find courses tailored to their background and professional aspirations. This page ensures that users can systematically build and enhance their HPC expertise by offering a structured competence-based approach.

Figure 30 - Skill Set (Data Structure).

3.4.4 Element/module listing page

For users looking to engage with more modular training approaches, the Element/Module Listing Page breaks down training sessions into smaller learning units (see Figure 31). Each module represents a specific topic or skill area within HPC training programs, enabling users to customise their learning journey by selecting relevant components. This modular approach is particularly beneficial for users seeking targeted knowledge acquisition, as it allows them to focus on particular aspects of HPC without committing to full-length courses. The listing page provides detailed descriptions of each module, including its duration, difficulty level, and relation to broader training tracks.

Figure 31 - Element/Module (Data Structure).

3.4.5 Track listing page

The Track Listing Page structures HPC training programs into thematic learning paths, guiding users through progressive skill-building journeys. Each track consists of multiple modules and training sessions designed to develop specific competences over time. Users can follow curated training paths that align with their professional development goals, whether they are researchers, industry professionals, or students entering the field of HPC. Training tracks are grouped by domain (e.g., computational modelling, parallel programming, machine learning in HPC), expertise level (beginner, intermediate, advanced), and application area. This structured approach ensures that learners can systematically advance their knowledge while tracking their progress.

Figure 32 - Track (Data Structure).

4 Conclusion & Outlook

Although the first version of *HPC in Europe Portal* has been made live with several enhanced features and functionalities, some functionalities remain partially inactive or in the development phase due to dependencies on external workflows. Efforts are underway to align and integrate contributions from all partners. Below, we list the following steps to achieve full implementation by the end of the project:

Integration of HPC SPECTRA

- All training events managed via HPC SPECTRA will be listed on *HPC in Europe Portal*, ensuring a centralised training repository.
- Attendees must first register as users of *HPC in Europe Portal* before signing up for training events.
- External platforms Indico (for training event registration and attendee management) and Zenodo (for storing training materials), which were mentioned previously, will be fully integrated.
- Ongoing coordination between *HPC in Europe Portal* and HPC SPECTRA development teams will continue, with integration taking place as soon as a stable version of HPC SPECTRA is ready. In Figure 33, we show the integration workflow.

Figure 33 - Integration of Spectra (Indico) into HPC in Europe Portal (C2ISS).

LinkHPC platform and integration with *HPC in Europe Portal*:

- LinkHPC will serve as an HPC services marketplace, connecting industry, universities, and SMEs (Small and medium enterprises) with available HPC services.
- The Waldur platform⁸ has been selected as the foundation for LinkHPC, with NCCs deploying their own Waldur instances.
- Once all NCCs have fully operational LinkHPC instances, they will be integrated into the *HPC in Europe Portal* through an “HPC Services” page, providing direct access to available LinkHPC instances.

⁸ Waldur platform: <https://waldur.com/>.

- **Integration of existing HPC-Portal data and users into the new *HPC in Europe Portal*:**
 - Integration of training content and existing users from existing HPC-Portal structure into upgraded HPC in Europe Portal structure.
 - Unused content types, outdated listing pages, and inactive user roles from the existing structure of HPC-Portal will be eliminated.
 - All users must be affiliated with an organisation (NCC, CoE or Project); alternatively, they will be assigned the Training Provider User role, allowing them to create only training-related content.
 - Existing training content will be restructured to align with HPC SPECTRA's training framework, ensuring compatibility with Indico-based event management.
 - Training event creation rules will change: Users can only create training events on behalf of their affiliated organisation, reinforcing structured role-based access.

- **Providing a content export facility for HPC community users:**
 - After the stable release of the *HPC in Europe Portal* (formerly known as C2ISS) platform, it is possible to provide a facility to export content from *HPC in Europe Portal* to any external platform through API data source of XML/JSON format.
 - Possible content types for export API would be included: Event, Training, News/Blog, Use Cases, and Success stories

- **Handbook guide and Workshop to educate Portal user more effectively**
 - It would also be included in the next step of planning to prepare a handbook guide for the portal users to help guide them on how to use the features and functionalities of a portal efficiently and more effectively.
 - Another helpful tool would be to organise a workshop to educate portal users, mainly Organisation-Admins and Members, on effectively managing organisation profiles and their belonging contents.

- **Expected timeline for achievements in year 3**
 - Release of stable version of *HPC in Europe Portal* (formerly known as C2ISS)
 - Expected timeline: End of March 2025
 - Transferring/Migration of data (Content) from EuroCC-Access & HPC CoE portals
 - Expected timeline: End of March 2025
 - Preparation of Handbook guide
 - Expected timeline: End of March 2025
 - User workshop for introduction and explaining main features of portal
 - Expected timeline: Start of April 2025

- User gets access to portal (Registration of User/Members) and starts using platform for publishing of new content, and no further content will be published on EuroCC-Access & HPC CoE portals.
→ Expected timeline: Start of April 2025
- To give feedback and suggestions
→ Until the End of April 2025
- Stepping down EuroCC-Access & HPC CoE portals and URLs are redirected to HPC Portal: End of June 2025

With these integrations, the *HPC in Europe Portal* will be fully established as a comprehensive and structured HPC knowledge hub by the end of the project. The successful implementation of the training management system, the integration and upgrade of existing HPC-Portal content and users, and the deployment of the LinkHPC marketplace will ensure that the platform is interoperable, sustainable, and user-friendly. These final phases will reinforce *HPC in Europe Portal* as a central European HPC resource for training, research, and industry collaboration, fostering long-term engagement and knowledge.

After these steps are achieved, this document will be further updated in Deliverable D5.6 - Explanatory report in the final version of the *HPC in Europe Portal* and the evolved EuroCC Access Portal. The upcoming deliverables and milestones are outlined in Table 2 and Table 3:

Number	Title	Due	Status
D5.2	Design strategy of the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC Access Portal	M9	Submitted
D5.4	Explanatory report on initial launch of the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC Access Portal	M15	Submitted
D5.6	Explanatory report in the final version of the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC Access Portal	M30	To be submitted

Table 2 - Overview of deliverables.

Number	Title	Due	Status
MS3	Design Strategy for the evolved EuroCC Access portal and the C2ISS are ready	M9	Completed
MS5	Evolved EuroCC Access portal is launched	M15	Completed
MS7	Final implementation of the evolved EuroCC Access portal and the C2ISS	M30	To be completed

Table 3 - Overview of CASTIEL2 WP5 milestones.